

GREAT GEOGRAPHICAL DISCOVERIES

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Abstract: In this article, concepts about the great geographical discoveries, the expedition of Christopher Columbus, the discovery of the American continent, the expedition of Magellan, the discovery of the sphericity of the earth and the integrity of the world ocean, the discovery of various new lands by traveling scientists are highlighted.

Key words: Great geographical discoveries, Christopher Columbus, Atlantic Ocean, India, American continent, "Renaissance".

(1) The era of great geographical discoveries is one of the important stages in the history of science. ". This work also signaled the beginning of a new era in the history of science.

Great geographical discoveries, in a certain sense, was a kind of rise in art, literature and science in Europe. at the beginning of the Western Europe, a number of centralized countries such as England, Spain, Portugal, France were formed in place of feudal disunity, and internal and external trade, money-goods relations were developing more and more. This, in turn, increased the demand for gold. In addition, the Ottoman Turks occupied Asia Minor, including Constantinople, and completely blocked European trade routes to the east. Western Europeans began to look for a route to countries with aromatic spices, gold and precious stones, such as China, India, and Sri Lanka, from the south through the Atlantic Ocean. As a result of this, a number of islands in the Atlantic Ocean, capes, gulfs, river confluences on the western edge of Africa and many places on the western edge of the African continent were discovered. These sea voyages, carried out on the eve of great geographical discoveries, were started by the Portuguese. Their efforts were supported by King Juan I and especially his son Prince Enrique. Enrique entered the history of geography as the main organizer and sponsor of these trips. It turned out later that the main purpose of this voyage of the Portuguese sailors was not to go to India or China, but to enter the gold-rich regions of the African continent, including Ethiopia. (2) Great geographical discoveries were made mainly in 3 directions. 1) south - across Africa, 2) west - across the Atlantic Ocean, 3) north - along the polar lands and northern coasts of Eurasia. (3) The beginning of the great geographical discoveries Sea voyagers from Portugal and Spain were the initiators of the great geographical discoveries. Fearless sailors were needed to realize such a grand idea. One of these travelers was the Genoese admiral Christopher Columbus (1451 - 1506). He planned to open a route to India through the Atlantic Ocean. Columbus managed to conclude an agreement with the Spanish royal family to equip an expedition to find the shortest sea route to India. The king undertook the financial support of the expedition. On August 6, 1492, Columbus led an expedition and set out to sea with three caravels. On October 12, 1492, the Columbus expedition landed on one of the islands of the Caribbean Sea. Columbus named the island San Salvador (now part of the Commonwealth of the Bahamas). Thus, the

search for the shortest sea route to India led to the discovery of America. However, Columbus did not realize that in 1492 he sailed not to India, but to America. He believed that he had come to India. That is why he called the natives Hindus. Columbus later equipped four more expeditions to India (actually America). As a result of these expeditions, many new lands were opened, where the Spanish flag was raised. These territories became the property of Spain. Columbus was appointed viceroy of these lands. The fact that the new continent was named America, not Columbia, is connected with the name of the Italian sailor and astronomer Amerigo Vespucci (1454-1512). In 1499 - 1501, he explored the coast of Brazil as part of a Portuguese expedition and came to this conclusion. The land discovered by Columbus is not India, but a new part of the world. He later named the continent the New World after himself. In 1507, the scientist-cartographer M. Waldzemuller proposed to name the new part of the world discovered by Columbus - America in honor of Amerigo Vespucci. The name was suitable for everyone. The first globe of the New World was named "America" in Germany in 1515.

Later, on other maps, the lands discovered by Columbus began to be called "America". The importance of great geographical discoveries. Great geographical discoveries played an important role in the development of many sciences. Geography, history, ethnography, oceanology were supplemented with new information and conclusions. Thanks to these discoveries, new trade sea routes were opened. The main maritime trade routes through the Mediterranean now moved to the Atlantic Ocean. These factors helped shape the subsequent world trade.

Thus, thanks to the Great Geographical Discoveries, the foundations of global civilization were laid. In 1498, the Portuguese expedition

of Vasco da Gama circumnavigated Africa and opened a sea route from Europe to India. In 1519 - 1521, the Spaniard Ferdinand Magellan's expedition traveled around the world. As a result, the sphericity of the earth was proved and the integrity of the world ocean became known.

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